

The impact of TED Talk videos on students' presentation performance

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Article Info

Article history:

Received Oct 31, 2023

Revised Dec 31, 2023

Accepted Jan 23, 2024

Keywords:

English as a foreign language

Higher education

Multimedia-enhanced

pedagogy

Performance

Presentation skills

TED Talk videos

ABSTRACT

This study investigated the impact of Technology, Entertainment, and Design (TED) Talk videos on students' presentation performance within the higher education context. Employing a quantitative approach, the study involved 14 first-year students enrolled in a "bachelor in English language" program at "Fan S. Noli" University, Korça, Albania. The research, conducted during the academic year 2022-2023 in "text analysis 1 and 2" modules, explores how the sequential exposure to TED Talk videos influences students' presentation skills. After watching the initial TED Talk video, students prepared and delivered one presentation, assessed using a rubric. Subsequently, students viewed 10 more TED Talk videos, with two presentations following these viewings. The study's analysis was facilitated using the statistical package for the social sciences (SPSS) version 20 software program. The Friedman and the Wilcoxon signed-rank tests were used to determine whether there are statistically significant differences among the groups in the repeated-measure design. The findings demonstrate that TED Talk videos play a significant role in enhancing students' presentation skills. This research contributes to the ongoing discourse on multimedia-enhanced pedagogy and the efficacy of integrating TED Talk as an educational resource, with SPSS version 20 aiding in the quantitative analysis of the obtained data.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Presentation skills are acknowledged as the most crucial ones for students to master in this technological era of higher education, as their primary function is communication. English is more than just an international language. Improvement and mastery of one's presentation and speaking abilities are among people's top investments across the globe, considering the four language skills. It enables individuals to share their messages with others and obtain the information or assistance they require. Speaking another language fluently is seen as a crucial quality for successful learners from all backgrounds [1]. Additionally, study by Demirel [2] noted that English is the most widely spoken language around the globe.

Despite this fact, presenting in front of a public is the hardest talent to learn [3]. Due to their limited vocabulary, ignorance of syntax, poor pronunciation, and speaking reluctance, students frequently feel lost when presenting a topic. University students need to be able to speak English, despite the fact that it can be challenging. Students should be able to communicate in English on a daily basis. But they actually do not practice speaking English very often, which prevents them from becoming proficient in it. When encouraged to speak, express an opinion, or answer, some of them exhibit passive behavior; they appear uninterested and

fearful [4]. According to Toubot *et al.* [5], students' anxiety levels increase due to less engaging classroom activities, a lack of cooperation, inappropriate teachers' teaching styles, demanding classroom environments, time constraints, or inappropriate teaching contents. The teacher should be able to help their students develop a passion for speaking English. They can use appropriate techniques or digital technology to improve their speaking quality during presentations.

In addition to the methodologies, media breakthroughs are also readily available. One of the most cutting-edge breakthroughs for teaching and learning is using videos. They can assist English as a foreign language (EFL) learner by offering them a sense of authenticity. Wagner [6] has suggested that the utilization of video accurately represents the real application of the English language. Authentic materials encompass spoken or written language produced in realistic communication contexts, rather than being specifically crafted for language instruction purposes. They can encompass several formats, such as television programs, feature films, songs, and similar media.

These sources provide inherent naturalness that enables them to effectively immerse learners in real-life contexts [7]. Nevertheless, EFL teachers may not be accustomed to utilizing these actual materials in their classrooms. However, it is crucial for students to engage with a diverse range of authentic materials to the greatest extent possible. This can facilitate the establishment of meaningful connections between the students' classroom environment and the broader real-world context. Furthermore, the utilization of authentic resources enhances students' motivation, concentration, and engagement in various educational endeavors to a greater extent than conventional materials [8]. Lialikhova [9] demonstrates that using video in the classroom offers a primary advantage by facilitating learners in attaining their educational objectives.

Therefore, the primary advantage of utilizing video for instructional purposes is its ability to enhance students' motivation to study English [10]. Furthermore, video, being a form of genuine resource, imparts multicultural awareness to the educational setting. EFL teachers should be aware of the crucial fact that English language instruction encompasses the teaching of grammar, vocabulary, and foreign cultures [8]. According to Wagner [6], using video in language instruction can benefit EFL teachers by offering them an opportunity to enhance learners' cultural awareness, acquainting them with various cultures, and improving their proficiency in the four English language skills while expanding their vocabulary as well. Videos can serve additional purposes, such as improving students' ability to communicate in the target language within their classroom. They are an active instructional tool in the classroom, as they push learners to engage and express their responses to the video's content.

Every learner has access to videos on a variety of subjects across all instructional domains [11]. One type of video is a Technology, Entertainment, and Design (TED) Talk. Since 1984, TED Talk has been a motivational video that shares experiences and inspires the audience [12]. TED is a nonprofit organization devoted to spreading ideas, usually in the form of short, powerful talks (18 minutes or less) [13]. It is an acceptable medium that can be utilized in speaking classes because, in accordance with Vasilevich [14], as stated in Farid [15], the speaker communicates their personal stories, ideas, and experiences with the audience, making TED Talk authentic. They are perfect examples from which students have a lot to learn.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The utilization of media is intricately connected to the utilization of language. Undoubtedly, media can expedite the students' presentation skills. Regarding the language itself, it holds immense importance globally, acting as the predominant medium of communication. People can express their thoughts, emotions, and ambitions through language, using both spoken and non-verbal means. TED Talk videos are a prominent illustration of an open-access platform for teaching and learning.

TED is an educational media organization that organizes global conferences and events. TED speaker sessions are available in video format on the TED website. These videos are accessible at any time and at any location [16]. TED Talk offer a focused and limited presentation that is frequently more motivating, imaginative, and captivating [17]. These talks are an innovation in popularization, breaking the traditional 'scientist-mediator-audience' triangularization by bringing scientists directly into contact with their audiences. The purpose of these educational pieces is to have a maximum duration of 18 minutes and address many important issues and concepts [18]. The contents encompass a diverse range of disciplines, spanning from entertainment to the instruction of language.

According to Anderson [19], TED initially started as a yearly conference that united the realms of technology, entertainment, and architecture. However, in recent years, it has expanded to encompass all topics that are of public interest [20]. There are TED Talk about almost every conceivable topic: technology, science, design, health, the environment, and personal growth. Currently, over 3,100 talks are available. Therefore, it is possible to find an inspiring talk for every individual student in the class. As supported by Nagarajan and Mohanasundaram [21], TED Talk is one of the web's most popular high-ranking video

networks, hosting numerous influential talk shows covering every subject, such as English. The TED short talks will have a huge effect on English language learners, along with the subject matter, to interactively develop vocabulary, pronunciation, grammar, and presentation skills.

TED Talk spark class conversation from an educator's point of view and help promote the interpretation of course content by the students and learners. Koç and Cephe [22] explored the use of TED Talk in English language pre-service teachers' education. It found that these talks enhance knowledge, broaden horizons, foster self-confidence, and improve language proficiency. Additionally, they fostered soft skills like autonomy, time management, and self-regulation. Taibi *et al.* [23] highlight the importance of TED Talk in classrooms as knowledge resources and instructional materials for language learning. Takaesu [24] examined at how college students' listening skills improved by using TED Talk as a great deal of listening material. He also looked at ways to modify the activity for students with lower competence levels. Based on two surveys and journal entries, the qualitative data analysis showed that students felt the lectures improved their listening comprehension, enhanced their motivation, and accustomed them to listening to a variety of English accents. Kozińska [25] showed that the participants' answers on the value of discussions around TED Talk confirmed the ideas of the communicative approach, based on which, when those learning are engaged in real communication, 'their natural strategies for language acquisition will be used'. Learning English with TED Talk is a supplementary resource for students participating in English language learning courses [26]. Students and teachers believe that one aim of using TED Talk videos is to improve students public speaking skills. So, this research is to focus on the impact of TED Talk videos on their ability to talk in public.

3. METHOD

3.1. Research design

The research adopts a quantitative approach in order to assess the degree to which the utilization of TED Talk videos contributes to the enhancement of presentation skills among higher education students. Data in this study are presented through table representations, and statistical methods are employed for analysis. The study's participants consist of 14 students within the age range of 18 to 22, all enrolled in the first academic year of the 2022-2023 academic year, pursuing the Bachelor's program in "English language" within the Department of Foreign Languages at the Faculty of Education and Philology, situated at "Fan S. Noli" University in Korçë, Albania.

3.2. Research hypotheses

The research hypotheses that this study is based on are: i) Exposure to TED Talk videos enhances students' presentation skills, as they provide real-life examples of effective public speaking, which can lead to improved presentation techniques and confidence (hypothesis 1); and ii) Engaging students with TED Talk videos as part of their educational curriculum positively impacts their academic performance, resulting in improved grades and overall educational outcomes (hypothesis 2).

3.3. Methodology for data collection

In pursuit of the requisite data for addressing the research hypotheses, the researcher employed a systematic protocol. Commencing the procedure, participants were tasked with viewing a video, followed by the delivery of an oral presentation. Subsequently, they were exposed to a series of two additional videos, each culminating in a presentation. This cycle of video exposure and presentation delivery was reiterated six times, with evaluative assessments being conducted in alignment with the specific criteria stipulated within the oral presentation rubric. Notably, the academic year 2022-2023 featured the usage of the "keynote, upper intermediate, students' book" for the modules "text analysis 1 and 2," which prominently integrated TED Talk videos. These TED Talk videos had a duration ranging from approximately 10 to 15 minutes, and a total of 11 videos were viewed by the participants. The students diligently prepared their oral presentations in advance and subsequently presented them before their peers a week following their initial exposure to the video content.

3.4. The evaluation of students' oral presentations

The evaluation of students' oral presentations is facilitated through the application of a specific assessment rubric. This assessment rubric comprises a set of criteria and corresponding point values, as outlined in Table 1. These criteria include the use of clear and comprehensible language (10 points), the incorporation of relatable examples (10 points), active engagement of the audience in the presentation's subject matter (10 points), adherence to a structured presentation format, including self-introduction and elaboration on the selected memorable event (10 points), as well as the demonstration of grammatical accuracy (10 points). The total possible score for each presentation is 50 points. Students are required to enter their names, the date of the presentation, and their assigned student number at the top of the rubric.

Table 1. The assessment rubric for the presentation [27]

Criteria	Points
a. Using words and phrases that are easy to understand to describe your memorable event.	10
b. Using examples that your audience can relate to.	10
c. Involving the audience in the topic of your presentation.	10
d. Following the steps:	10
- Introduce yourself and the topic.	
- Say what memorable event you want to talk about.	
- Give more details and examples.	
- Finish the presentation.	
e. Using correct grammar	10
Total score	50

3.5. The instrument of the research

The instrument used in this study for data collection is a combination of observation and data analysis facilitated by the statistical software program statistical package for the social sciences (SPSS) version 20. The observation is used as a primary method for data collection. Participants are observed as they engage in a structured process that involves watching TED Talk videos and subsequently delivering oral presentations. The observations encompass various aspects of the presentation, including language clarity, use of examples, audience engagement, structured format, and grammatical accuracy. These observations are conducted systematically and are crucial in assessing the quality of the students' presentations. Observation as a data collection method allows researchers to gather real-time information about the participants' performance and behavior. In this case, it helps in assessing how students apply the skills and knowledge they may have gained from watching TED Talk videos in their actual presentations.

The data collected through observation, such as the scores and other relevant information related to the oral presentations, is then subjected to analysis using SPSS version 20. It is a widely-used statistical software program that provides the tools and capabilities necessary for data processing and statistical analysis. It is employed to calculate descriptive statistics such as mean scores, standard deviations, and medians. Statistical tests, such as Friedman's test and the Wilcoxon signed ranks test, are utilized to determine the significance of differences between presentations and pairs of presentations. SPSS version 20 performs these tests, helping to determine whether the observed variations in data are statistically significant.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Students' scores of the sixth presentations

The researcher evaluated the data after each of the six presentations to compare the students' oral presentation skills after watching TED Talk videos. The scores of students on the presentations are displayed in Table 2. It is seen that the total scores increase progressively from presentation 1 to presentation 6, indicating potential improvement in the quality of the presentations over time. There is variability in individual student scores within each presentation. For example, in presentation 1, student scores range from 19 to 40, demonstrating a spread in performance. This variability is present in most presentations.

Table 2. Students' scores of the sixth presentations

	Presentation 1	Presentation 2	Presentation 3	Presentation 4	Presentation 5	Presentation 6
Student 1	20	27	30	35	40	41
Student 2	24	25	35	36	42	43
Student 3	30	32	35	37	46	44
Student 4	32	37	38	40	43	45
Student 5	19	28	30	44	39	44
Student 6	34	22	34	40	42	41
Student 7	21	23	34	36	40	42
Student 8	30	40	45	50	50	50
Student 9	24	45	50	49	50	49
Student 10	36	40	45	50	50	50
Student 11	37	40	43	44	47	48
Student 12	40	44	50	49	50	50
Student 13	39	45	50	50	49	50
Student 14	22	38	45	50	50	50
Total score	408	486	564	610	638	647

From presentation 1 to presentation 6, it is observed an overall upward trend in total scores. This suggests that, on average, the presentations were better received or performed better as the presentations progressed. In some presentations, there might be outliers where a few students significantly outperformed or

underperformed compared to their peers. These outliers can be important to identify, as they might provide insights into factors affecting scores. Students 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, and 14 consistently scored high in most presentations, with some reaching the maximum score (50) in the later presentations. This group of students seems to be consistently strong presenters.

On the other hand, there were some students, such as student 1, 5, and 7, generally scored lower than their peers in most presentations. It may be beneficial to provide additional support or guidance to help these students improve their presentation skills. Presentation 6 has the highest total score, and this could be an indication that the final presentation was the best received or most effectively delivered by the students.

The trend of increasing scores suggests that the students have improved their presentation skills over time. This is due to the effect of watching TED Talk videos, practice, feedback, or experience gained during the course. To perform a more detailed analysis, it is needed to calculate mean scores, standard deviations, and look for correlations between presentations.

4.2. The analysis of the standard deviations and mean score of the presentations

This part delves into an in-depth examination of the presentations, emphasizing crucial statistical metrics to assess the overall effectiveness. Important information about the score distribution is provided in Table 3, which also shows the mean and standard deviations for each presentation. Finding patterns, variances, and primary tendencies in the data set is the goal of this in-depth analysis, which will provide a nuanced picture of the presentations' overall efficacy.

There is a noticeable increase in the mean scores from presentation 1 to presentation 6. The scores progressively increase from 29.1 to 46.2. This suggests that the quality or performance of the presentations may have improved over time or that the content and delivery of presentation 6 were better received than presentation 1. This indicates some variability in the quality or effectiveness of the presentations.

Table 3. The standard deviations and mean score of the presentation

Statistics	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6
Mean	29.14	34.71	40.29	43.57	45.57	46.21
Median	30.00	37.50	40.50	44.00	46.50	46.50
Std. Deviation	7.410	8.334	7.384	6.085	4.380	3.683

4.3. The results of Friedman's test

To study the statistical significance of the observed increase, Friedman's test, a non-parametric statistical procedure, was employed within the SPSS version 20 software platform. The choice of this test is due to the nature of the variables under investigation and aims to discern variances in the performance scores attained by students across multiple presentations. The ensuing test outcomes, as illustrated in the subjoined Tables 4 and 5 reveal a statistically significant discrepancy, denoted by a p-value (sig.) of less than 0.05, (sig=0<0.05), signifying that the disparities observed are not likely due to random chance but hold statistical significance.

As it is seen from the results in the table, presentation 1 has the lowest mean rank (1.11), which suggests it had the lowest values in the data. Presentation 6 has the highest mean rank (5.29), indicating it had the highest values. The mean ranks of the other options fall between these two extremes.

The Chi-square statistic is 59.517. In the context of the Friedman test, this statistic is used to test whether there are significant differences among the groups. The degrees of freedom for the chi-square statistic are 5. This suggests that there were six groups (P1 to P6) under consideration (df=k-1, where k is the number of groups). The p-value is extremely low (0.000), which indicates that there is strong evidence to reject the null hypothesis. This means that there are significant differences among the groups in the study. The ranks and mean ranks provide a sense of the relative performance of the groups (P1 to P6), with P1 having the lowest mean rank and P6 having the highest. The test statistics, particularly the Chi-square and the low p-value, confirm that there are statistically significant differences among these groups.

Table 4. The mean rank

Presentation	Mean rank
P1	1.11
P2	1.93
P3	3.43
P4	4.29
P5	4.96
P6	5.29

Table 5. The results of freedman test

Test statistics	
N	14
Chi-square	59.517
df	5
Asymp. Sig.	.000

4.4. The results of post hoc analysis of Wilcoxon signed ranks

In order to study in which pairs of variables there is a statistically significant difference. The post hoc analysis of the Wilcoxon signed ranks test was used in SPSS version 20 by studying each pair of presentations (1-6). The results are displayed in Table 6.

Table 6. The Wilcoxon signed ranks test scores

Presentation	Z	Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	Presentation	Z	Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)
P2-P1	-2.544 ^b	.011	P6-P2	-3.299 ^b	.001
P3-P1	-3.186 ^b	.001	P4-P3	-2.851 ^b	.004
P4-P1	-3.298 ^b	.001	P5-P3	-2.992 ^b	.003
P5-P1	-3.302 ^b	.001	P6-P3	-2.995 ^b	.003
P6-P1	-3.299 ^b	.001	P5-P4	-2.006 ^b	.045
P4-P2	-3.301 ^b	.001	P6-P5	-1.308 ^b	.191
P5-P2	-3.298 ^b	.001	P6-P4	-2.530 ^b	.011

As it is seen from the results, the only case in which there is no statistically significant difference is when examining P5 and P6, ($\text{sig}=0.191>0.05$), i.e. respectively presentations 5 and 6 which, although characterized by a higher average than the other presentations, with each other have no statistically significant difference. In all other cases, the studied pairs have a statistically significant difference ($\text{sig}=0<0.05$). This study examined the impact of using TED Talk videos to improve students' presentation skills in higher education. The researcher collected the data on students' scores on the assessment rubrics per presentation and analyzed them to find the mean score. The mean score of the first presentation was 29.1. This result is after students watched only one video. In this TED Talk video entitled "404: *The Story of a Page Not Found*," the speaker, Renny Gleeson, talked about how companies could use messages saying that web pages could not be found on the server to communicate with their online audience [28].

Students' presentations aimed to describe a memorable event. First, all the students introduced themselves and the topic, but they needed to give examples that the audience could relate to. They needed clarification to follow all the instructions they had in the rubric. Most students should have provided more details and examples and used the phrases suggested in the rubric. Students needed to be more confident in what they introduced to their peers. Students made some grammar mistakes throughout their presentations owing to their level of anxiety.

The mean score for the second presentation was 34.7. Students watched the TED Talk video "Keep your goals to yourself." The speaker, Derek Sivers, said that telling other people about your personal goals will reduce your chances of actually achieving them. The other TED Talk video was "Global population growth, box by box" by Hans Rosling [28]. He used props to show the audience what global population growth meant and how the world changed [28]. So, the second presentation aimed to describe their goals by using props. Students brought humor into the class, as many props were hilarious. They enjoyed this experience very much. At the same time, students created a sense of intrigue and curiosity in the class. The audience was active and involved in the presentations. Some of the students made some grammar mistakes as they got confused when altering the props on the PowerPoint slides.

The mean score of the third presentation was 40.2. It rose by 11% compared to the second presentation. The TED Talk video that students watched was entitled "Success is a continuous journey" by Richard St. John. He outlined that to achieve sustainable success, we needed to do work that we loved and constantly strive for success. The other TED Talk video was "Got a meeting? Let's walk" by Nilofer Merchant. She talks about how physical activity and fresh air can help us think outside the box at work [28]. The third presentation aimed to make a persuasive argument [28]. The results showed that students were getting used to preparing and presenting the presentations to the audience. The majority of them made a solid opening statement. They surprised the audience by saying something they did not expect. Some of them could have given more details concerning their arguments. They all finished the presentations correctly.

Relating to the fourth presentation, its mean score was 43.5. The rise was by 6.6% compared to the third presentation. Students watched the TED Talk video "Please, please, please. Let's put the 'awe' back in 'awesome'," by Jill Shargaa. She draws attention to the fact that we often misuse the word awesome because its original meaning has become lost. The other TED Talk video was "The sore problem of prosthetic limbs" by David Sengeh [28]. He talks about how he used technology to develop more comfortable amputee prosthetics. So, the fourth presentation aimed to present something they love to do. Their level of confidence increased while presenting [28]. They had more eye contact with the audience. The majority of students was very authentic and described the things they loved. They were relaxed and friendly with their peers. The slides of the presentations showed their personality. However, some students needed to explain why they loved the things they had chosen.

As far as the fifth presentation is concerned, it aims to explain a process. The mean score of the students' results was 45.5. It increased by 4% compared to the fourth presentation. Students watched the TED Talk video "*How to Make Work-Life Balance Work*" by Nigel Marsh. He talks about what he has learned from his experience trying to find a good work-life balance and gives the audience advice on how they can achieve that [28]. The other TED Talk video was about "*Doodler, Unite!*" by Sunni Brown. She proposed that while doodling was usually frowned upon and discouraged, it could help us unlock our creativity [28].

After students watched these two videos, they had to prepare a presentation in which they had to explain a process. The majority of students kept their ideas simple. They used simple visuals that were easy to understand. They also limited their slides to two or three points. Despite these, some students still needed to say what the topic meant to them.

The mean score of the students' results in the sixth presentation was 46.2. It increased by 1.4% compared to the fifth presentation and 34.2% compared to the first. Students learned more from concrete examples of TED Talk videos and how presenters were confident onstage. The following TED Talk video that students watched was about "*5 ways to listen better*" by Julian Treasure. He pointed out that we do not consciously listen to most of what we hear; focusing on what he called 'conscious listening' could help us build more meaningful relationships with the people around us [28].

The last video they watched was about "*Cloudy with a Chance of Joy*." In this TED Talk video, Gavin Pretor-Pinney used examples of cloud spotting to draw attention to the fact that we do not spend enough time doing nothing and enjoying life and the world around us [28]. With those two videos as examples, students prepared the report on PowerPoint slides and presented it in front of the class. Most of them used gestures to present the data they had included in the graphs. Their bodies were calm and still. However, two students were too emotional and did not move their arms or hands. All the students followed the presentation steps correctly and used correct grammar.

Referring to hypothesis 1, the increasing trend in scores indicates potential improvement in the presentation quality of the student's scores for their oral presentations. The discussion of individual student scores highlights variations among students, both in their performance and how they responded to the intervention. Some students consistently performed well, while others struggled. The observation of presentation 6 having the highest total score suggests that the final presentation may have benefited from cumulative learning, reinforcing the idea that TED Talk videos could have a positive impact on presentation skills over time. The increase in mean scores from presentation 1 to presentation 6 indicates an overall improvement in presentation quality. The low standard deviations in the later presentations (P5 and P6) suggest that there was less variability in student performance, implying that the presentations were more consistently well-received.

Friedman's test is employed to test the statistical significance of the observed increase in mean scores. The results indicate a significant difference among the presentations, with a very low p-value (0.000). This provides strong evidence to reject the null hypothesis, indicating that the presentations did indeed vary significantly across the six sessions.

The post hoc analysis further explores where statistically significant differences exist among the pairs of presentations. This analysis identifies the differences and similarities in presentation quality. It is interesting to note that the only case where no statistically significant difference is observed is between presentations 5 and 6, indicating that students performed consistently well in these later sessions.

As far as hypothesis 2 is concerned, exposure to TED Talk videos may positively influence academic performance by enhancing communication skills, critical thinking, and student engagement, potentially leading to better grades. This aligns with modern educational goals that prioritize real-world applicability, critical thinking, and effective communication, as TED Talk often feature experts from various fields.

Using multimedia content like TED Talk can make learning more engaging and interactive, fostering greater student interest and, consequently, improving academic performance. Modeling behavior is essential to learning, according to Bandura theory of social learning [29]. Students witness speakers employing a variety of methods to engage and establish rapport with the audience when they attend TED presentations, such as storytelling and questioning. They watch while various presentation strategies are put into effect. Learning from more experienced and knowledgeable speakers may also align with Vygotsky's concept of the zone of proximal development, which states that one can acquire knowledge from a more experienced person that they otherwise would not be able to acquire on their own [30]. More than a dozen research are cited by Berk [31] to support the use of film or video in the classroom. Similarly, multimedia enables leadership educators to present ideas in fresh and creative ways that grab students' interest, spark meaningful conversation, and produce dialogue to emphasize challenging or complex concepts [32], [33].

The hypothesis extends beyond better grades, proposing that students may achieve overall improved educational outcomes, including deeper subject understanding, enhanced problem-solving abilities, and a

more comprehensive educational experience. However, empirical evidence is needed to confirm these claims, necessitating research to measure the actual impact of integrating TED Talk videos into the curriculum on students' grades and educational outcomes. It is crucial to acknowledge that academic performance is influenced by various factors beyond TED Talk videos, such as teaching methods, student motivation, and curriculum design. To fully evaluate the hypothesis, the long-term effects of using TED Talk in education should be considered. So, there was a positive correlation between watching videos and the students' presentation scores. They exhibited enhanced self-assurance and significantly refined their abilities in delivering presentations.

5. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this paper has explored the impact of using TED Talk videos to improve students' presentation skills in higher education. The results of the study indicate a positive correlation between exposure to TED Talk videos and students' presentation scores. The mean scores progressively increased from the first presentation to the sixth, demonstrating a potential improvement in the quality of the presentations over time. Students exhibited enhanced confidence and refined their presentation skills as they gained experience from watching these real-life examples of effective public speaking.

The findings align with the first hypothesis, which suggests that exposure to TED Talk videos enhances students' presentation skills. The increase in mean scores, the significant differences observed through statistical tests, and the overall improvement in presentation quality support this hypothesis. TED Talk videos provide students with valuable insights into effective public speaking, thereby contributing to improved presentation techniques and confidence.

Additionally, the study considered the second hypothesis, which posits that engaging students with TED Talk videos positively impacts their academic performance and overall educational outcomes. While the study did not directly measure academic performance, the enhanced presentation skills and engagement observed can contribute to better grades and a more comprehensive educational experience. It is essential to recognize that academic performance is influenced by multiple factors, and the impact of using multimedia content like TED Talk should be considered alongside other educational elements.

This study underscores the significance of integrating real-life examples of effective communication into the curriculum to enhance students' presentation skills. The implications of the findings extend beyond the classroom; as effective presentation skills are a valuable asset in various professional settings. By leveraging multimedia resources like TED Talk videos, educators can promote not only improved presentation skills but also critical thinking, student engagement, and overall educational outcomes.

While this study provides valuable insights into the positive impact of using TED Talk videos in higher education, further research is necessary to explore the long-term effects of this approach and its influence on academic performance. Additionally, investigating the interplay between various teaching methods, student motivation, and curriculum design will offer a more comprehensive understanding of the factors that contribute to enhanced educational outcomes. In conclusion, the results emphasize the potential of multimedia resources like TED Talk to enrich the educational experience, foster effective communication, and prepare students for success in the ever-evolving landscape of higher education and beyond.

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